

Organic Derivatives of Germanium. Part IV. Application of Ammonia Method in the Synthesis of Diphenyl- and Tributyl-alkoxygermanes

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Several diphenyl and tributyl alkoxides of the type $\text{Ph}_2\text{Ge}(\text{OR})_2$ and Bu_3GeOR (where R=Me, Et, Prⁿ, Buⁿ, Bu^t, and Bu^s) have been prepared by passing ammonia gas as proton-acceptor in a solution of diphenyl- or tributyl-germanium chlorides in an excess of alcohol in presence of benzene.

Several metal alkoxides have been prepared by passing dry ammonia gas in a solution of metal chloride in an excess of alcohol. Ammonia gas acts as a proton-acceptor in these reactions. Presence of benzene helps in reducing solubility of ammonium chloride formed in the alcohol.

Germanium tetra-alkoxides have also been prepared by Bradley *et al.*¹ by the above method. Several tri-alkylgermanium alkoxides have been synthesised by Lesbre and Satge² by taking tri-alkylgermanes and alcohol in presence of copper as a catalyst. They² have also prepared tri-alkylgermanium alkoxides by the sodium method. West *et al.*³ synthesised these alkoxides by the reaction of methylgermanium chloride with sodium alkoxides. Brook⁴ also employed the sodium method for the synthesis of triphenyl-alkoxygermanes.

The advantages of using the ammonia method have already been described in an earlier communication dealing with corresponding silicon derivatives⁵. The synthesis of dibutyl-di-alkoxygermanes by the ammonia method has been reported⁶. In the present communication, we have extended the utility of this method to the preparation of diphenyl- and tributyl-alkoxygermanes. This method has been found to be convenient and alkoxides can be prepared in high yields.

The tributylalkoxygermanes are all colorless, distillable, mobile liquids. The diphenylalkoxygermanes are comparatively high-boiling, viscous, colorless liquids. Molecular weight determinations of these compounds show them to be monomeric. Refractive indices of these compounds have also been measured.

1. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1953, 746.
2. *Compt. rend.*, 1962, 254, 4051.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 310.
4. *Ibid.*, 1955, 77, 4927.
5. Mehrotra and Pant, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 65.
6. Mathur *et al.*, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1965, 4, 294.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus with standard interchangeable joints were used throughout and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Alcohols were dried over sodium metal, magnesium ribbon, or azeotropically as the case may be. Alkylgermanium chlorides were distilled before use. The reactions were carried out in presence of dry benzene (first over sodium wire, then azeotropically with ethanol). Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in boiling benzene in a semi-micro Gallenkamp ebulliometer. Refractive indices were measured by an Abbe refractometer. The alkoxy contents were ascertained by the oxidimetric method⁷ and germanium was estimated as tributyl- or diphenylgermanium oxide by hydrolysing the alkoxide in aqueous parent alcohol and drying it at 110-120° in an electric oven for 2 hr. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out at Microanalytical Laboratory, Amsterdam.

General Method of Synthesis

Dry ammonia gas (passed through a battery of aluminium isopropoxide towers) was slowly bubbled into a solution of diphenyl- or tributylgermanium chloride in an excess of alcohol in presence of benzene (70-75 ml). The reaction started with the slow formation of ammonium chloride and an appreciable amount of heat was liberated after some time. Supply of ammonia gas was discontinued when the reaction mixture was cooled to the room temperature. It was allowed to stand overnight and next day, when ammonium chloride settled, it was separated by filtering the reaction mixture in vacuum. The filtrate was concentrated by distilling unchanged alcohol and benzene. The diphenyl- or tributyl-alkoxides were distilled under reduced pressure. Data for these alkyl alkoxygermanes are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Diphenyl dialkoxygermanes.

Diphenyl-dichloro-germane.	Alcohol added.	Formula of the product.	B.P. /mm.	Mol. Wt.		Ref. index.	Found. Reqd.	
			*Yield(%).	Found.	Calc.		C.	H.
6.8 g.	10 g.	$\text{Ph}_2\text{Ge}(\text{OMe})_2$	119-22°/0.5 (91)	296	288.8	1.5405	C: 57.37% H: 5.31 Ge: 25.00 OR: 20.80	58.21% 5.58 25.14 21.47
10.6	15	$\text{Ph}_2\text{Ge}(\text{OEt})_2$	130-32°/1.0 (86)	301	317.0	1.5400	C: 58.00 H: 6.00 Ge: 23.00 OR: 28.43	60.00 6.58 23.00 28.40
11.5	17	$\text{Ph}_2\text{Ge}(\text{OPr})_2$	129-30°/0.7 (84)	339	345.0	1.5247	C: 61.10 H: 6.97 Ge: 20.99 OR: 34.15	62.00 7.01 21.04 34.24
5.2	9	$\text{Ph}_2\text{Ge}(\text{OBu}^n)_2$	154-55°/0.6 (91)	382	373.0	1.5240	C: 63.65 H: 7.86 Ge: 19.80	64.4 7.66 19.46
4.2	5	$\text{Ph}_2\text{Ge}(\text{OBu}^t)_2$	124-25°/0.2 (75)	350	373.0	1.5130	C: 63.75 H: 7.73 Ge: 19.51	64.4 7.56 19.46
5.0	8	$\text{Ph}_2\text{Ge}(\text{OBu}^i)_2$	152-53°/2.5 (85)	377	373.0	1.5210	C: 63.81 H: 7.67 Ge: 19.40	64.40 7.66 19.46

*Shown in parenthesis.

7. Bradley, *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450,

TABLE II

Trialkyl alkoxgermanes from trialkyl monochlorogermans.

S. No.	Bu ₃ GeCl.	ROH.	B.P./mm.	Yield.	Mol. Wt.		Ref. index.	Found.	Reqd.
					Found.	Calc.			
1.	5.0 g.	MeOH (5 g.)	128-32/0.5mm	93%	280	274.00	1.4480	Ge: 25.45 % OR: 11.54	26.40 % 11.28
2.	11.0	EtOH (9.0 g)	125-28°/8	75	201	288.05	1.4440	Ge: 24.75 OR: 16.03	25.12 15.59
3.	10.8	PrOH (14 g.)	127-30°/7	68	301	302.00	1.4400	Ge: 23.68 OR: 19.74	23.96 19.50
4.	5.8	ButOH (7 g.)	136-40°/8	70	314	317.00	1.4420	Ge: 22.41	22.91

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